

ALL-Ready Project Deliverable 2.6

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

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Towards a Network of European Agroecology Living Labs: Advancing the agroecology transition using living labs and research infrastructures

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List of abbreviations

AE	Agroecology
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
LL	Living Lab
NCP	National Contact Point
OIA	Open Innovation Arrangement
RI	Research Infrastructure
R&I	Research and innovation
SC	Societal Challenge
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs and Research Infrastructures that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

ALL-Ready forms part of the foundation for the preparation of the candidate Horizon Europe Partnership 'Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures'. The ambition of this report is to summarise and synthesize the findings of the ALL-Ready tasks that map and analyse the barriers and opportunities for agroecology transition, and to make recommendations for further advancing agroecology transition with living labs (LLs) and research infrastructures (RIs) as key research and innovation (R&I) mechanisms, chiefly at the level of primary production.

This ambition goes beyond that of the grant agreement, which stipulates merely summarizing and synthesizing WP2 efforts with respect to the mapping of LLs as, during ALL-Ready implementation, it was found that a report with a broader overview of complementing findings, and which also covers RIs, would be of considerable value to ALL-Ready and the candidate partnership. Indeed, in the latter, as well as in ALL-Ready, LLs and RIs are seen as linked mechanisms for fostering agroecology transition, with the building of LLs/RIs capacity and network(s) as key activities. However, LLs in the current report, remain the main focus of attention. The raised ambition has led to later submission than originally stipulated.

This report draws on not only WP2 ALL-Ready mapping reports, but also on outcomes from the ALL-Ready work carried out in relation with implementation and sustainability of the network (see page 8) and capacity building. ALL-Ready reports drawn on are listed under 'Internal References' in the bibliography.

The results of drawing on a wide set of reports from ALL-Ready in this deliverable, and the subsequent triangulation is summarised and synthesised in the last section of the report. The present report also makes reference to the wider academic literature.

This report is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 briefly outlines the key concepts and the background for the report.
- Chapter 3 presents the key findings on the barriers for capacity building, challenges for LLs and RIs, funding needs and the policy drivers of agroecology transition.
- Chapter 4 provides a synthesis of the main conclusions and provides recommendations for advancing agroecology transition, specifically as regards policy and capacity building for networks of LLs and RIs.

2. Conceptual background

The mapping in ALL-Ready has focused on 4 key areas that are highly interlinked: (I) capacity needs for implementing LLs and RIs, (II) challenges and needs faced by LLs and RIs, (III) funding; and, (IV) policies. These are areas generally perceived to affect – as barriers or enablers – agroecology transition, within a framework where knowledge generation and exchange are seen as central elements (see: Wezel et al 2020) for fostering transition, by means of LLs and RIs as key mechanisms (MACS 18). Given the complexity and interlinked nature of agroecology transition, we should perceive the mentioned areas as elements that are important when working towards integrated systemic solutions (Alrøe & Noe, 2014).

Mapping in the present context is understood in two ways: as mapping of characteristics and definitions within Europe, and as a *scoping review*, e.g. as a synthesis that identifies key concepts, gaps of various kinds, types and sources of evidence to inform practice, policy-making and research. The present mapping therefore, along the lines of a scoping review, deals with the 'broader topics where many different scientific traditions, study designs, and types of evidence may exist' (Pedersen et al 2020: p. 5).

The report's transition focus aligns it with the flourishing field of sustainability transition and transformation literature that has evolved over the past 3 decades. As Geels (2019) suggests, approaches to sustainability transition are a contested area that includes socio-technical and social-ecological thinking. The spectrum of approaches also includes political ecology approaches, in which natural resources are located within a social framework of distribution, and where access to resources is key to transition and transformation (see Ribot, 2013). However, the present emphasis on mapping LL and RIs in contexts of public policy drivers, and to some extent (cultural) 'meanings', with data collected from policy, research and civil society levels, connotes predominantly socio-technical perspectives.

The socio-technical and multi-level perspective (Geels, 2019) is particularly evident in relation to the agroecology transition focus of the ALL-Ready mapping exercise, which reflects the perspective that actors at various levels, but mainly associated with national agricultural knowledge and innovation systems (AKIS), can nurture "innovation so it becomes more robust through performance improvements and expansions in supportive sociotechnical networks" (Smith & Raven, 2012: p. 1025). Within this framework, policy agendas that aim to enable the overcoming of barriers such as locked-in socio-technical regimes, and eventually lead to transition, stem from coalitions of civil society and experts who manage to influence policy agendas.

This coalition dynamic is evident in agroecology's trajectory from a 'niche' concern to policy level (Levidow et al, 2014) as manifested in the planned European Partnership on *Accelerating Agroecology Transition: Living Labs and Research Infrastructures* that the ALL-Ready mapping supports. The socio-technical approach of the Partnership, both with regards to its evolution and in terms of ambition to nurture innovation for transition, is evident in the so-called Partnership Dossier¹.

In ALL-Ready, the socio-technical approach to mapping is supplemented by characterisations and definitions of what constitutes agroecology production systems and agroecosystem LLs and RIs as part of innovation and transition processes (see: ALL-Ready Deliverable 1.2 *Definitions and a set of inclusion criteria for agroecology living labs, pertinent research infrastructures and their synergies* and McPhee et al., 2021). For LLs, these characteristics are presented in Table 1.

¹ See: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/bb604022-acee-4ebd-bcd7-a6c1e0688385_en?filename=european_partnership_for_accelerating_farming_systems_transition_march_2022.pdf

Table 1 Defining characteristics of Agroecosystems Living Labs

Table 4. Defining characteristics of agroecosystem living labs.

Dimension	Characteristics
Aims	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aimed at sustainability and resilience of agriculture and agri-food systems • Innovation can be expressed through technology, best management practices, or processes • Knowledge production and knowledge network creation
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exceptionally high level of evaluation and data management • Long/seasonal innovation cycles with high uncertainty due to external factors • Scaling up and out to outcomes at the level of agriculture and agri-food systems
Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasis on public sector researcher participation • User roles may be diverse and can evolve • Often driven by the public sector or academic institutions • High diversity and number of partners, interests, and values requiring complex governance schemes
Context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The living lab is embedded within and examined at the scale of agroecosystems

From McPhee et al 2021, p. 1718

As evident from Table 1, the characteristics of LLs are, to a considerable extent, associated with multi-level participation in innovation processes and integration of socio-technical regime actors. Given the complexity and uncertainties related to the transition of agroecosystems and the focus on user-driven innovation, LLs can be an essential component in improving the coordination of knowledge production by supporting research gaps identified by practitioners (McPhee et al., 2021). Further, showcasing sustainable solutions in practice-based settings and designing national policies that present these solutions in specific contexts can strengthen farmers' capacities and abilities to adopt agroecological practices (Beaudoin et al., 2022).

Finally, agroecosystem living labs, characterised by sustainability aims in contexts of diverse user roles and interests, complex governance arrangements and community involvement, invoke the concept of rural, often community-based institutions of cooperation. Over the past couple of decades, these have become prominent in rural development policy, as ways of organizing innovation and economic activities at local levels (see Berg 2014). Such institutions, built on norms, cultures, rules etc, are arenas where various interests are pursued, and which define fields of action for both individuals and groups. They are constituted chiefly by social and economic relations in combination (Bromley 2009), specifically by broadly defined social relations of cooperation, negotiation, competition and power (Lund 2006). Indeed, the scope and ambition of living labs often go beyond mere research to also act as vehicles for solving mosaics of challenges and 'wicked' natural resource problems (Head et al 2016) through collaborative processes and collective action (Ostrom 1990). Rural institutions of cooperation may take many shapes but as social capital their relevance is clear: Pretty et al (2020) on the basis of a meta-analysis, suggest a correlation between the existence of rural community based institutions and capacity for change towards sustainability. The study concludes that the higher the presence of cooperative arrangements, the higher the likelihood that communities, broadly understood, will be able to transition towards sustainability.

3. Scope and core definitions used in the mapping of barriers and enablers to agroecology transition

The ALL-Ready project, in line with FAO, defines agroecology as “an integrated approach that simultaneously applies ecological and social concepts and principles to the design and management of food and agricultural systems. It seeks to optimise the interactions between plants, animals, humans and the environment while taking into consideration the social aspects that need to be addressed for a sustainable and fair food system” (FAO, 2018).

With respect to LLs, the report *Definitions and a set of inclusion criteria for agroecology living labs, pertinent research infrastructures and their synergies* (D1.2) in line with ENoLL (<https://enoll.org/about-us/what-are-living-labs/>), define these as open innovation arrangements (OIAs) based on principles of co-creation, user involvement, and real-life contexts. They represent networks of a diverse set of participating actors, including farmers, advisors, value chain actors, civil society and researchers from various technical, natural, social, and human sciences, and facilitate the rapid exchange of knowledge among them. The innovation process in LLs is characterised by co-creation, demonstration and iteration. These labs aim to drive social transformation through business knowledge and social values.

The same report defines agroecology RIs as research facilities that allow for the observation, experimentation, design and prediction of agroecosystem and agri-food redesign. They can be managed by agricultural or research and development organisations and are considered relevant if they are installed for a long-term period (5-10 years) and align with agroecological principles.

Why map capacity needs for advancing agroecology transition with LLs?

The rationale for the mapping of capacity needs of actors associated with agroecology transition may be summarised as follows:

First, it is acknowledged that actors involved in open innovation for agroecology transition, whether in research, policy or farming practice, need to internalise agroecology principles (see Wezel et al 2020 for the consolidated agroecological principles and elements based on HLPE (2019) and FAO (2018)) and adopt inter- and cross-disciplinary approaches to address what are often mosaics of complexity (Wezel et al 2009, Wezel et al 2020).

Secondly, transition to agroecology is seen to depend on place-specific solutions, with socio-ecological and environmental conditions varying in time and space according to local circumstances. Converting agroecological principles into place-specific solutions requires clear understanding of the agricultural, socio-economic and cultural context of the regions/areas (see Pretty et al 2018). Because of this context specificity, agroecological innovation cannot rely on standard designs (Altieri et al 2011) but requires considerable knowledge sharing to address complex and interrelated challenges (Wezel et al 2009).

In this context, co-creation is seen as a key instrument that allows for knowledge generation: farmers, advisory services, as well as other actors in the value chain need to be engaged in co-creating innovations inspired by the principles of agroecology for transition to take place (see Partnership Dossier 2022). In general, end-user involvement is highlighted as a key element for agroecological innovation, as context-specific solutions require the integration of tacit knowledge. End-users must be open to innovation, to testing new procedures, ideas or activities to discover their properties, behaviour and/or effects.

In policy, LLs are seen as increasingly central to implementing agroecology transition and thus adopted as key rural institutions in primary production (see section 2) in the European Green Deal. These LLs are understood as practice-driven institutions that facilitate and foster open, collaborative innovation, in real-life settings, offering open (off-station) and user-driven innovation where new solutions are developed, (see McPhee et al 2021).

The methodology applied in the mapping of capacity needs for agroecology transition, along with results, are summarised in the following:

Framework for mapping competencies needed to support LLs in fostering transition to agroecology

Mapping of capacity needs was aimed at, in a first step, understanding which competencies are of particular importance in supporting LLs and RIs for fostering agroecology transition. According to Spencer and Spencer (1993), competencies are best described and visualised as an iceberg, with a person's knowledge and skills representing the visible tip of the iceberg, and with foundational enduring personal characteristics or self-concepts, traits and motives (for example, self-confidence, initiative, empathy, achievement orientation, etc.) representing the larger portion of the iceberg, hidden below the waterline. Whereas knowledge and skills can be easily advanced through training and education, the characteristics below the surface are rather difficult to assess and develop (see *'Skills and Competencies Framework, D 5.2*).

To understand which competencies are important for accelerating transition at the level of an agroecology LL or RI, the ALL-Ready mapping team co-created a competencies framework together with the members of the ALL-Ready pilot network of LLs and RIs. This framework was first applied when interviewing national contact points² (NCPs) and other initiatives at a December 2021 joint workshop as part of the kick-off meeting of a pilot European Network of Agroecology LLs and RIs. During that workshop, data was collected on competencies for managing LLs and RIs on agroecology, as well as on the needs for capacity building for each of the pilot members. Data collection was complemented in relation to the added value of the European Network of Agroecology LLs and RIs. A total of 11 interviews were conducted among existing LLs and RIs.

We identified 5 main sets of competencies required to contribute to agroecology transition:

a) Common understanding on agroecology:

The concept and practice of agroecology has evolved over a long period of time and continues to develop. Initially, it was related to production-related approaches in farming systems by combining the perspectives of agronomy and agriculture with ecology. At later stages, it was broadened to food systems by including environmental, economic, social, political and ethical dimensions. At present, it is conceptualised as a practice, a science and a social movement with the objective to enable transition of farm and food systems. It is indicated that these three dimensions of agroecology should all be seen as important dimensions of agroecology and mutually constitutive driving forces. However, our results suggest that the concept is still not well known in general. Agroecology is often associated with one or two of these dimensions. In particular, **a clear understanding of the social dimensions of agroecology** is not sufficiently developed.

b) Agroecological practices:

Agroecological principles can be applied to farming systems and the wider food system. Our results indicate that the emphasis is mainly on the application of these principles in primary production and much less on the broader food system. In addition, there is still insufficient insight into the impact of agroecological practices. What do we consider as agroecological practices and **what is the ecological but also the socio-economic impact of these**

² NCPs are, by the EC, considered essential components in the implementation of successive Framework Programmes, providing information and on-the ground advice to potential applicants and beneficiaries (EC, 2022). In the ALL-Ready mapping, NCPs were defined as stakeholders from a combination of living labs, farmers associations/civil society, research and policy/funders.

practices and systems? An inventory of agroecological practices and the evidence base around these practices was requested in several countries.

c) Systems thinking:

EU agri-food systems are facing challenges and structural changes that are accelerating under the influence of societal demands, social and economic changes and upheavals, increasing environmental degradation (e.g. biodiversity loss, reduced soil and water quality) and the adverse effects of climate change. These challenges and their effects are both complex and interconnected. Systems thinking is needed to fully grasp path dependencies and lock-ins, and to assess both short and long-term consequences. Only by fully grasping this, and being able to frame problems, will collectively creating and crafting alternative agroecological pathways be possible. Our results indicate that systems thinking needs to be further developed among various stakeholder groups to properly represent the holistic perspective in agroecology transition and the connection between different research areas. Systems thinking is needed to approach agroecology not as a set of single practices but as a systems approach. Researchers are sometimes very focused on a particular topic/practice or scientific discipline but do not see how this might benefit or fit agroecology transition as a systems approach.

d) Co-creation and transdisciplinary approaches:

The need for transdisciplinarity has already been alluded to above. Added to this is that that agroecology transition requires collective approaches (see section 2), and hence novel ways of designing and implementing collective interventions, transitions, and transformative governance strategies towards sustainability. Farmers will need to be supported and guided to set up experiments and investigate the impact in systemic ways. Co-creation of innovation requires competencies to interact with different participants involved in the transition process. This entails anticipation skills such as the ability to jointly envision and design rich future visions related to sustainability issues, along with problem-solving frameworks and transition strategies. It involves skills in the areas of communication, negotiation, leadership and collaboration, which are important for successful cooperation among stakeholders. Our results indicate that further improvement of the coordination between science, practice and policy makers is something that needs to be developed.

e) Scientific foundations of agroecology:

Related to systems and transdisciplinary thinking, agroecology transition requires approaches that bring together scientific knowledge and practical knowledge. Our results suggest that there is a particular need for a holistic approach to the challenges facing our farm and food systems. The respondents in the mapping exercise especially pointed out the already mentioned lack of a social dimension in research projects, and experienced this as an important hindrance to conceptualise a full understanding of the challenges in many agri-food systems. Some respondents also indicated that the importance of traditional ecological knowledge is underestimated. Besides this, tools need to be developed to understand the impact of agroecological practices by developing monitoring tools that can be applied in the field.

3.1. Overview of the needs of LLs and RIs

In the following chapter we deal with competencies more indirectly and summarise key findings of the mapping of concrete needs and challenges faced by LLs and RIs in implementing and managing R&I for agroecology transition.

Overview of challenges and activities of LLs and RIs

Agroecology LLs and RIs face a variety of challenges and needs related to the implementation and the management of their R&I activities. Based on this knowledge, the survey tool for

mapping challenges and needs of LLs and RIs is based on ALL-Ready's vision and mission (D1.3), as well as the questionnaire developed to operationalise the inclusion criteria (D1.2). The survey tool (<https://sondages.inrae.fr/index.php/458632>) based on self-evaluation was used to collect information on key characteristics, activities, values and the maturity of agroecology LLs and RIs across Europe and to help organisations understand the extent to which they engage in the agroecology transition. Thirty-three initiatives beyond the ALL-Ready pilot network members responded to the survey. Seven initiatives described themselves as LLs, 9 as RIs and 6 as other OIAs. In addition, 10 initiatives defined themselves as both LLs and RIs and OIAs, as the questions were not limited to one possible answer, and 1 initiative served as a platform promoting R&I funding for organic farming actors.

Most initiatives that have participated in the survey are actively involved in co-creation activities, often by bringing together farmers and other participants to collaborate and validate outcomes. The initiatives actively involve users, and where experiments are conducted, then training is often provided in real-life contexts. The majority of initiatives aim to promote resilience and sustainability, for example by making agroecosystems more resilient to climate change, extreme weather events and other disturbances. They also prioritise diversity, whether in land use at different scales, or for crop and livestock production.

The initiatives aim to support climate change mitigation and environmental adaptation by promoting 'responsible' agriculture. This is manifested in various practices, such as utilising biological and integrated pest management, reducing tillage, safeguarding domestic pollinators, improving animal welfare and health and implementing measures to sequester carbon in soil and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Most organisations aim to promote the efficient and responsible use of natural resources, though it is often limited to one or two of the described activities.

A common activity reported in the survey was a reduction in the use of pesticides, veterinary drugs, fertilisers and non-chemical soil and agronomic inputs. Reducing energy usage and recycling biomass and organic matter is not yet a priority for several initiatives, though it is planned for the future. Participation in activities that foster synergies among the various functions of ecosystems is somewhat limited. However, a few initiatives are taking the lead in this regard, while others are eager to do so in the future. Many initiatives are also actively involved in creating circular and solidarity economies and in supporting local food production.

In order to further improve the understanding of the particular challenges, needs and expectations of LLs, RIs and other OIAs engaged in agroecology transition (some of which have already been reported here), in-depth interviews were conducted with selected survey respondents and funding organisations. Interviews were conducted with 13 LLs, RIs and other OIAs as well as 8 funding organisations. The criteria for selecting initiatives for the interviews considered that their needs and challenges are likely to differ depending on the level of experience and stage of development of the initiative, the access to and history of funding, the scope and complexities of multi-actor engagement and the inclusion of examples from the different main geographic European regions (see *Report on the added value of the European Network. D4.1* for more details on the interviews).

Based on inputs from the survey and interviews, challenges have been put into main categories, including maintaining innovations and overcoming barriers of adoption, long-term sustainability, stakeholder engagement and the understanding and application of the LL methodology, data management and ownership (*Report on the added value of the European Network. D4.1*).

a) Maintaining innovations and overcoming barriers of adoption

It is a key challenge to LLs and RIs to stay innovative, i.e. addressing social and technological innovations and improved management practices considered innovative by academia (e.g. in relation to water management, biodiversity, and soil health), while, at the same time, maintaining long-standing research programmes to develop practical solutions. These include farmer-led research, on-farm trials and field experiments (e.g. plant breeding, intercropping, weed management, and new pesticides and fertilisers). Documentation and measurement of effects of the new solutions (e.g. treatments and practices) is needed to enhance knowledge and raise awareness of their sustainability benefits in order to increase acceptance and adoption. Intergenerational aspects in farm management also need to be addressed, combining traditional knowledge with the readiness for adopting innovations of younger farmers who are moving back to the rural areas (with new attitudes).

Additionally, innovation challenges relate to high levels of bureaucracy in project administration and the management of multiple differences in actor compositions and activities. There is a need for more flexibility in administrating R&I actions to account for changes in the work and outcomes. The ability to pay for services provided by farmers (including on-farm experiments) and other key actors is also needed.

b) Long-term economic sustainability and accounting

Challenges and needs related to the long-term economic sustainability of LLs and RIs are linked to the funding issues and gaps summarised in section 3.2 (e.g. long-term funding, improved communication on the use and benefits of funds). In addition, resilience against pandemics such as the COVID-19 pandemic was a challenge for the maintenance of R&I activities of several initiatives. It impacted on project delivery as the lock-downs made it impossible to carry out activities and measurements.

c) End-user engagement and collaboration

A common challenge that agroecology LLs and RIs face is to convince end-users (primarily farmers and smaller companies) to take part in the initiative. This applies in particular to farmers, perceived as reluctant with respect to being innovative in an agroecology context and as somewhat unwilling to adopt agroecological practices.

Related to this, difficulties are faced with respect to convincing farmers of the wisdom of shifting to agroecological practices, with reluctance in this regard being perceived as lack of knowledge and awareness of economic and market opportunities of agroecological farming on the part of farmers. Further challenges relate to convincing farmers to test new practices on their own fields, practice research in a collaborative setting, and the sharing of information while ensuring confidentiality.

Given the often large number of stakeholders that are involved in a LL or a similar initiative, the level of information sharing between stakeholders is sometimes insufficient. Some stakeholders or companies are hesitant to share information and data with a group. The development of trusted relationships between the stakeholders is a long-term process and requires good soft and social skills on the part of facilitators and coordinators of the initiatives.

d) Understanding and applying the Living Lab concept and methodology

LLs are relatively new to researchers and in many cases not really known among other stakeholders. Uncertainty about the approach results in a reluctance to engage and cooperate. Methodological guidance is seen to be needed on how to develop and apply participatory methods through trial and error, on how to build environments of trust with farmers and stakeholders and on how to communicate with a large group of stakeholders to reach common understandings of key issues and concepts.

Applying the LL concept on transition to agroecology thinking necessitates a move from purely practice-based thinking to systems thinking. This requires close collaboration between social and natural sciences and a need for further awareness-raising amongst funders and scientists on the importance of involving and funding socioeconomic aspects. Strengthening systems thinking is a key theme for capacity building, e.g. for fostering the development and improved governance of local food systems in agroecology transition.

Further challenges arise from the consideration of different scales of LLs. For example, solutions for value chains and market development for transitions to agroecology may not always be local and actors to be involved may come from different areas. Also, some of the wider ecosystem services, and related users, may require a wider coverage of a LL, which can increase the complexity of its management.

e) Challenges related to data management

Data-related issues reported in the survey include lack of data sharing and the need for suitable common data platforms and conflicts regarding data ownership and property rights. Particular challenges highlighted for RIs relate to the interdisciplinary and long-term nature of experiments as well as to transboundary data management across RIs in different countries.

In addition to those challenges briefly summarised above, access to funding is a common challenge for most LLs and RIs. Funding issues and gaps, as mapped in ALL-Ready are discussed in more detail in the following section.

3.2. Agroecology-related funding instruments and funding gaps

The creation of the European Research Area (ERA) in 2000 was a significant development for R&I in the EU. The ERA was instrumental in establishing new mechanisms for transnational cooperation and funding by pulling together national scientific resources around identified thematic priorities. How has this process been relevant for building agroecology research in Europe?

In concrete terms, H2020 Societal Challenges (SC), particularly SC2 'Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the Bioeconomy' together with SC5 'Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials' have provided a platform for work on relevant aspects of sustainable agriculture. Under SC2, agroecology was indicated as an example of an agricultural system, together with organic and agroforestry, including multiple references to sustainable agriculture and climate (EC, 2020a). Agroecology transition was perceived as a pathway towards a broader transition of the agri-food system.

Horizon Europe has a focused policy framework where R&I activities under cluster 6 ('Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment') will contribute to the objectives of the European Green Deal and specifically to the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, the Farm to Fork strategy, the European Climate Pact and initiatives contributing to sustainable industry and eliminating pollution, as well as the long-term vision for rural areas, and the Sustainable Development Goals. Horizon Europe has yet to uncover its full potential in relation to agroecology transition, which is expected to be achieved primarily through launching of the new funding instrument European Partnership on Agroecology.

The present analysis focused on the extent to which research funding led to, or likely will contribute to agroecology R&I initiatives and European level synergies. With our screening of EU funded projects, we tried to tackle several important questions. We decided to use the Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS) as it is the European Commission's primary source of results on projects funded by the EU's framework

programmes (FP) for R&I and lists projects from FP1 to Horizon 2020. We used CORDIS to screen EU research projects based on selected specific target words.

The screening period started with FP7 projects in 2007 and ended with ongoing H2020 projects that began before March 2022 (when the search ended). Out of the 295 projects identified, the vast majority was funded under H2020: 242 projects including 9 ERC, and only 53 were funded under FP7 projects. The overall budget put into these projects over the time period of 15 years was 1,376,480,904€, while the average budget per project was 4,666,036.96€. In total, 13,446 months of work time (1,120.5 years) were financed by the EU, which is equivalent to an average of 45.6 months per project. In the most recent years, an increasing number of agroecology-related and relevant projects were funded than in the first years of the study period.

Out of the 295 projects, 214 were joint projects in which at least 2 (or often 5 or more) European countries collaborated, while in 81 projects, it was an initiative from a single country without European collaboration. In total, organisations from 39 European countries (also some countries from other continents were involved, but are not included here) participated in the projects (see D2.2). The amount of participation in the projects varied significantly among countries of Europe, as some countries are much bigger than others, and therefore contain more relevant organisations or have just obtained higher budgets and increased manpower.

Furthermore, it appears that in some countries the interest in transforming conventional agriculture to agroecology is much further developed than in others. Initiatives from Spain (174 projects, 59% of all the projects being present) represented the ones that have been involved in the most EU projects of our search, closely followed by Italy, the UK, Germany and France. Smaller countries such as Belgium and Denmark were also involved in a relatively high number of projects.

We assigned each project to a certain thematic category of agroecology, for instance with main focus on ecosystem and biodiversity protection, reduction of waste and pesticides, bioenergy or rural and socio-economic development. Each project could also fall into several categories at the same time. We did that based on their project description and objectives, in the CORDIS database. In total, we worked with 13 thematic categories. The category which we identified as the most commonly found was 'agroecology technologies and innovation', capturing inventions that can foster agroecology, followed by projects that deal with 'crops, fruits and vegetables' as well as projects about 'ecosystem and biodiversity protection'. Projects that were linked to 'agroforestry', 'bioenergy' and 'food distribution' were identified with much lower numbers. One reason for these low numbers could be that these categories are often overlooked when it comes to agroecology as they are not classical 'farm land' categories, or are not a direct component of the food system. Probably a broader range of people in the agricultural sector see innovation in the agricultural system as linked to innovation of technologies.

Overall, our analyses showed that there are (expected) differences over time, space and agroecology categories. These differences should be analysed and interpreted carefully to make sure the transition process is fostered all across Europe and that funds are spent wisely and mistakes are not repeated. For instance, funding gaps for research and innovation activities should be identified. The interviews described in section 3.1 have been conducted with the aim of contributing to such a process, i.e. a) to identify funding gaps that hinder further engagement of LLs and RIs in transition to agroecology and b) to improve the understanding of the challenges and needs of funding organisations to enhance the effectiveness of their funding (see *Report on the added value of the European Network. D 4.1*) for more details on the interviews).

Access to funding is a common challenge for most LLs and RIs. One challenge, for instance, is to successfully integrate LL activities into applications for Horizon Europe R&I funding programmes, due to high competition for these programmes. The Horizon Europe

programmes provide more substantial amounts of funding than local programmes, but successfully applying for these funds requires a large amount of time and resources.

A number of initiatives have highlighted specific funding gaps. These relate to long-term funding and funding for follow-up activities and management of the LLs after an initial round of project funding. Funding gaps are also frequently an issue for practice partners on the ground (lack of eligibility of practical business-related activities). Companies that are developing technological innovations get funding in the beginning of the development, but they lack funding in the product launch phase. As a consequence, many solutions are not launched due to lack of funding for testing and demonstration as well as risk aversity. In addition, initiatives highlighted the need to find ways to fund farmers for their expertise and on-farm experiments. Important funding gaps also exist for training, demonstration and fostering social innovation. A common issue for research organisations or networks is the low level of basic funding for maintaining the different infrastructures (e.g. greenhouses, laboratories and collection orchards) and costs for maintaining these are increasing (problem of higher energy costs). In parallel to project-related funding for carrying out specific R&I actions, long-term funds are needed for financing permanent staff members to manage and maintain RIs and networks.

The need for a stronger consideration of funding the long-term management of LLs and RIs is mirrored in the responses of the funding organisations. Main themes of challenges and needs from the perspective of funding organisations are the funding of networking activities and long-term management, communication and capacity building, relevance to end users, political and private interests, and cooperation and coherence between funds. There is a need for improved communication on the use of funds between initiatives and funders.

Supporting long-term funding strategies is a key benefit that the interviewed LLs and RIs and funding organisations expect from a European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures. Solutions have to be found that value the different aspects of agroecology, visible within the funding business plan, as agroecology has a wide range of facets. This should be visible and picture diversity at the level of geography, but also thematic categories and practices in the future. In the best case, policy-makers should receive recommendations on how to ensure that funding addresses the needs of actors engaging in transitions to agroecology and provides added value for society.

3.3. Supporting policies and contextual perspectives on agroecology transition

As for the already mentioned ALL-Ready mapping activities, National Contact Points (NCPs) were the main entry point for providing an overview of the enabling environment for agroecology transition. In this case NCPs were grouped into three categories (a. policy/funding, b. research and c. living labs, civil society). Given the role of these agricultural knowledge and innovation system (AKIS)-related actors as key drivers for the establishment of local LLs as experimental and learning hubs in projects funded under Horizon Europe, they were a highly relevant entry-point for gaining an overview of national initiatives and experiences. NCPs from the policy sector were identified, initially through FACCE-JPI, a Europe-wide initiative that focuses on agriculture and food security in light of climate change and which has expertise in research programming and funding. Further, contacts within the research sector were identified by identifying participants in agroecology-related projects under Horizon 2020, while LL and civil society actors were identified through a combination of existing networks of project partners, the ALL-Ready pilot network and snowballing methodology. To the extent possible, the country-specific investigations entailed interviews with all three categories of these key informants.

The ALL-Ready report *Drivers of Agroecology Transition* (D2.3) confirms suggestions in key literature that environmental and institutional conditions differ substantially across national contexts, which has implications for how respondents conceptualise agroecology and the

drivers of the agroecology transition (see for instance Metzger et al. (2005) and Klerkx, van Mierlo, and Leeuwis (2012); Knierim et al. (2015)). As pointed out in earlier sections, within and across Europe, there is substantial variation in perceptions of agroecology and the importance of different dimensions of agroecology.

Generally, the perception of agroecology as a scientific discipline tends to be of most importance in the North-Eastern parts of Europe. Further, agroecology as a social movement tends to be of less importance within countries in the northern parts of Europe, while it is more pronounced in the southern parts of Europe. Although the agroecology concept is generally not well recognised, the investigation suggests that a number of agroecological practices are widely used among practitioners.

Table 2 Replies to the question: "To which extent do you agree with the following statements regarding opportunities for a transition towards agroecology-based practices and research infrastructures?"

		Current national policies sufficiently foster agroecology transition	Current European policies sufficiently foster agroecology transition	Resource allocation is sufficient to support agroecology transition	Advisory systems sufficiently foster agroecology transition	A transition towards agroecology-based practices is seen as a societal concern in my country	The current organisation of the food market supports agroecology initiatives	The underlying values of the current agriculture and food production system sufficiently foster an agroecology transition
NW Europe	Belgium	Yellow	Grey	Yellow	Yellow	Grey	Yellow	Yellow
	Denmark	Yellow	Grey	Yellow	Grey	Grey	Yellow	Yellow
	Finland	Yellow	Grey	Yellow	Grey	Yellow	Yellow	Grey
	Germany	Grey	Blue	Yellow	Blue	Grey	Grey	Yellow
	Iceland	Yellow	Grey	Yellow	Blue	Grey	Grey	Grey
	Ireland	Grey	Blue	Yellow	Grey	Grey	Yellow	Yellow
	Lichtenstein	Yellow	Yellow	White	Grey	Grey	Grey	Grey
	Luxembourg	Grey	Blue	Yellow	Grey	Blue	Yellow	Yellow
	Norway	Grey	Grey	Yellow	Blue	Grey	Grey	Grey
	the Netherlands	Grey	Grey	Yellow	Grey	Grey	Yellow	Yellow
	Switzerland	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Blue	Yellow	Yellow
United Kingdom	Yellow	Blue	Yellow	Grey	Grey	Yellow	Yellow	
NE Europe	Czech	Grey	Blue	Yellow	Yellow	Grey	Yellow	Yellow
	Estonia	Grey	Blue	Grey	Grey	Blue	Grey	Grey
	Hungary	Yellow	Blue	Yellow	Yellow	Grey	Yellow	Yellow
	Latvia	Grey	Blue	Yellow	Grey	Grey	Grey	Yellow
	Lithuania	Blue	Grey	Yellow	Grey	Blue	Grey	Grey
	Poland	Yellow	Grey	Yellow	Grey	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
	Slovakia	Grey	Blue	Yellow	Yellow	Blue	Blue	Blue

S Europe	Cyprus							
	France							
	Serbia							
	Turkey							
	Average							
		Fully agree	Agree	Neutral	Partly disagree	Disagree	No data	

With respect to policies in support of agroecology transition, the investigation carried out in ALL-Ready indicates that while some principles and practices associated with agroecology transition feature prominently in current policy making, others do not. Certain practices, such as fertiliser and manure management, diversified crop rotation and integrated pest management using biological control, are generally well supported in national policy-making. Wetland restoration using paludiculture and multi-stakeholder innovation are other key practices that are only sustained to a smaller extent in a number of countries.

Although the green transition now features quite prominently in European agro-food policies, most notably in the Green Deal, our findings indicate a range of shortcomings in current policies, including the lack of emphasis on knowledge transfer, the need to strengthen advisory systems, and a need to provide incentives for agroecology transition.

Further, a number of respondents across different countries discussed the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and its ability to support agroecology transition. Generally, it is argued across a number of reports that although the CAP is the most important foundation for agri-food development in terms of funding, it is generally not conducive to agroecology transition but rather used to sustain agroindustry. Hence, there is a need to strengthen the coherence of policy actions for green transition to ensure that regulation aligns with the ambitions they advance (such as agroecology transition). Aside from the financial support provided by the CAP, different regulatory initiatives that ban harmful practices and regulate farmers' conduct with respect to biodiversity, aquatic environment and soils are also emphasised as important elements of agroecology transition

With respect to the overall opportunities for transition to agroecology, interviews with NCPs indicate a number of shortcomings (see table 2). Specifically, respondents indicate a range of shortcomings pertaining to current policies, including a lacking emphasis on knowledge transfer, insufficient attention to the need for strengthening advisory systems and to providing incentives for agroecology transition. NCPs from most countries indicate that domestic policies are not sufficient to foster agroecology transition.

However, other European policies than the CAP are seen as relatively adequate. This implies that domestic implementation of European policies and supporting national policy development in the years going forward should be a high priority. Given the highly contextualised nature of transitions to agroecology, this is an important element that may have been neglected as the agri-environmental policy agenda has been highly influenced by European policies and directives in the past three decades. Add to this that, particularly in the Southern and Eastern parts of Europe, advisory systems are assessed to be insufficient to support agroecology transition.

In terms of the underlying values and organisation of the food market, stakeholders report insufficiencies across the vast majority of the countries in the assessment. This suggests that transitioning to agroecology presupposes a more fundamental and systemic reorientation of key institutions that underpin current production systems, including those associated with both producers and consumers and the underlying policy, knowledge and market drivers. Looking towards the upcoming partnership and the development of LLs, this implies a need to promote institutions to encompass all actors and ensure that the transition

process is designed to initiate changes in the wider innovation value-chain underpinning the farming system. A transition to agroecology is not just a technical and agronomic matter, it also concerns the organisation of the entire farming and food systems and will not be viable if these supporting institutions are not also aligned (Röös et al., 2022, Moschitz et al., 2021).

4. Concluding synthesis and recommendations

Bringing together the mapping of LLs, RIs and other OIAs carried out in the frame of ALL-Ready, has entailed analysis of a number of qualitative investigations into enablers and barriers to agroecology transition, as perceived by key stakeholders, predominantly agroecology and LL practitioners/civil society organisations, researchers (often associated with RIs) and representatives of authorities. While the barriers and enablers of agroecology transition reported are both structural (e.g. policy, funding) and more operational (e.g. needs felt by LLs for capacity building) understanding the linkages between the two levels is important for interventions to be effective.

For instance, the different capacity building needs felt by LL actors across geographical areas affect abilities to effectively foster agroecology transition. This challenge may usefully be understood in the context of the strengths or weaknesses of national and regional agricultural knowledge and innovation systems (AKIS), to which survey respondents are directly or indirectly linked. Indeed, the studies confirm that levels of integration of AKIS elements, i.e. farmers, researchers, and advisory systems with the underpinning public policy that is needed to support AKIS actors as sociotechnical transition networks (Smith & Raven, 2012: p. 1025) are key indicators of barriers and enablers to agroecology transition.

While levels of AKIS integration and strengths may be associated with access to funding and knowledge in particular, place-specific factors that influence agri-food organising and governance practices and perceptions of agroecology (while indeed influencing AKIS) also constitute barriers and enablers. However, detailed analysis of these factors is beyond the scope of this report.

4.1. Research funding

In overall terms, the funds available in the past couple of decades in EU R&I programmes for sustainability-related topics in agriculture, have reached Central, Eastern and South-Eastern Europe only to limited extents. The reported low levels of basic funding for research, including that for RIs in many countries in these regions, exacerbate this situation.

While low levels of AKIS integration and funding appear somewhat correlated, the challenges surrounding funding go beyond geographical skewedness. Overall, respondents find cause for concern with regards to what is perceived as funding gaps for the open innovation activities that are associated with LLs, also in the current Horizon Europe programme, and point out that funding for activities beyond scientific experimentation, including training, demonstration, processes of social mobilisation and networking is limited. Indeed, multi-stakeholder innovation and other key participation-based knowledge generation practices are reportedly only sustained in a few countries. This funding design issue is related to one of the most commonly reported challenges: the need for longer-term funding horizons for research in and by LLs, and the associated lengthy and often non-linear processes required to ensure collaborative, participatory research, with users at the center.

Current challenges point to the need for a research paradigm shift towards more open innovation with research in LLs and other OIAs. This shift appears to entail, for some research funders, rethinking the perceptions of what actually constitutes R&I and indeed 'research excellence', to the extent that this dominating concept connotes mainly on-station experimentation and metrics associated with publications, citations, patents etc.

4.2. Perceptions and use of agroecology in policy and practice

Indeed, heterogeneity across Europe is evident not only with respect to the strength of AKIS and funding, it also manifests itself with respect to perceptions of agroecology: the mapping reveals considerable variation with respect to emphasis given to the understanding of the concept as 'practice', 'science' or 'movement' with 'practice' and 'science' understandings dominating in Northern and Western Europe. However, regardless of how agroecology is understood and defined, the generally limited understanding of the concept across Europe, particularly the social dimensions and the implications of agroecological pathways in terms of both agriculture and socio-economic dimensions, acts as a barrier to transition.

In particular, it is felt by LL practitioners/civil society organisations that better understandings will enhance their abilities to frame agendas, work in more cross-disciplinary fashion and foster collective action for agroecology transition. In sum, enhanced understandings of the agroecology concept and its various facets may enable LLs and civil society stakeholders to play more substantial roles in agroecology transition.

4.3. Barriers associated with LLs and RIs

As for agroecology, however it is defined, the concept of LLs is novel in many parts of Europe, and barriers faced by farmers and other LL practitioners reflect this novelty, in particular as regards methodological capacities for implementation:

As reported, respondents generally experience difficulties with regards to setting up farm experiments, structuring co-creation processes and joint monitoring and evaluating as well as documenting and communicating on progress and results, i.e. the sharing of knowledge. Lack of such skills, as felt by some, leads to problems of 'staying innovative' which again hampers the ability of LLs to convince other (conventional and sometimes seen as risk-averse) farmers of the wisdom of adopting new agricultural practices. Linked to this adoption challenge, respondents have also pointed out the well-known 'aging farmer population' and succession problematic as both a structural and an operational barrier to innovation. It is well known that younger, well-educated farmers are more innovative and less risk averse than their older peers.

Both the methodological and the generational succession challenges faced by LLs are at the heart of agroecology transition models in which co-creation, knowledge sharing and networking are key dynamics (see Wezel et al 2020). This serves as a reminder that the introduction of LLs as key innovation institutions in agroecology transition demands targeted and not 'one size fit all' blueprint approaches on the part of facilitators. With reference to 4.1, above, implementing R&I through LLs will also require methodological capacity strengthening with respect to the design and validation of experiments, that integrate the open, user driven R&I model associated with LLs with the more researcher-controlled practices of RIs.

4.4. Policies: Supportive or not?

The investigations find that domestic policies support a range of principles and practices associated with agroecology: in particular, fertiliser and manure management, diversified crop rotation and integrated pest management. However, possibly reflecting weak understanding of the agroecology concept (see 4.2), these policies are rarely associated with agroecology transition; rather, respondents point to the influence of agri-environmental policies leveraged by EU directives in past decades. The fact that EU policies are seen to be more supportive than national policies for agroecology transition, (even if the CAP is not seen as supportive) appears to be testament to the importance of EU directional leverage.

The extent to which policy – at domestic and at EU level – is considered supportive of agroecology transition reflects the barriers reported in 4.2 and 4.3. AKIS are seen to be insufficient for fostering transition, and more so in Southern and Eastern parts of Europe.

This renders these innovation systems ill-equipped to promote multi-stakeholder innovation and other key user-centered knowledge generation practices. Indeed, considering that the involvement of end-users is an important element of research for agroecology transition, poor relationships between farmers, advisory services and the research community are a serious barrier.

Additionally, as also suggested in 4.3, institutional arrangements have implications for LL capacities to act as 'drivers of transition' at all levels in AKIS and policy (framing issues, advocacy, applying for funding etc.). This state of affairs brings us back to the key transition dynamics also mentioned in 4.3, and the role of knowledge sharing through networking as a key transition dynamic (Wezel et al 2020). Networks of LLs appear all the more important in the context of weak AKIS.

It needs to be stressed that even if AKIS capacities are geographically skewed across Europe, policy shortcomings are reported across all the countries that were mapped, with AKIS often reported to lack systems and transdisciplinary perspectives and hence the systems thinking required for agroecology transition. Moreover, a number of respondents find that the values that underpin agri-food production systems do not work in favor of transition towards agroecology.

This all suggests that agroecology transition requires a more fundamental reorientation of different AKIS subsystems, including research, practices and supporting policies to accommodate transition, and that transition to agroecology-based production systems is not merely a technical and agronomic matter, but also concerns the organisation of the entire production system and its institutions, including the market.

4.5. Summary of recommendations for the promotion of agroecology transition through LLs and RIs

The various mapping endeavors of ALL-Ready have generated a number of recommendations for enabling agroecology transition with LLs and RIs as central elements, in networks linked with AKIS. These are summed up as follows:

Recommendations for capacity building of LLs and RIs:

- Strengthen methodological guidance and methodological development for LLs, including the structuring of LLs, the facilitation of participatory processes, communication etc.
- Strengthen capacities of LLs to design and document scientific experimentation. This will contribute to addressing the integration of LLs and RIs and the bridging of scientific paradigms.
- Strengthen capacities of RIs to engage in open innovation arrangements such as LLs, including issues of transdisciplinarity, validation, access policies and changing research paradigms.
- Strengthen capacities of LLs to document and detail innovation through e.g. institutionalised monitoring and evaluation processes, thereby enabling LLs to articulate needs for longer project horizons for funders.
- Enhance understanding amongst AKIS stakeholders with particular focus on LLs, of agroecology and transition concepts, to enable these to act as proactive, social innovation forces in transition, that frame and scope issues and set agendas.
- While generational succession is a barrier that is rooted in the wider structural constraints that face agriculture, developing methods for the targeting of young farmers should be an integral part of capacity building.

Policy recommendations:

- Design agile funding arrangements, nationally and transnationally, to reflect the need for relatively longer timescales needed for research in LLs compared to traditional research institutions.
- Design funding arrangements for research in LLs to enable payment to farmers for experimental activities.
- Strengthen the capacity of AKIS, both advisory systems and formal research, to implement agroecology transition.
- Apply differentiated approaches to strengthen the capacity of AKIS, considering geographical 'hotspots' where AKIS are particularly weak.
- Linked to the above, ensure that initiatives for the strengthening LLs through networks (of networks) are designed to strengthen overall AKIS, and not merely the LL element of AKIS. This may not only contribute to transition at national levels but also contribute to EU green transition ambitions and policies being better understood and better implemented at national levels.
- Ensure a diverse involvement of funders and distribution of funding in terms of geographical balance as well as thematic areas related to a successful and diverse transition to agroecology throughout Europe.

Appendix A: Opportunities for advancing agroecology-based practices

Table 3. ALL-Ready partners' synthesis of the interviews with respect to the entry: "Opportunities for advancing agroecology-based practices"

Belgium	<p>All interviewees see for the moment many hindering factors among which the most relevant ones are :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the market that is organised on standardisation - high volumes - long chain and doesn't take into account social and environmental costs - New technology and investments are mainly aimed at intensive farming systems - No clear policy that supports agroecology - Time dimension: it takes time before agroecological practices start to show off the benefits - need for long term monitoring and research - The big difference between the citizen (demands a lot of farmers concerning health, animal welfare, environment) and the consumer (who wants to buy the food for the cheapest price that doesn't take into account externalities of food production) - Agriculture in Flanders is characterised by intensive agricultural production, especially livestock production. Prices for agricultural land are extremely high, so there is an ongoing debate on 'land sharing versus land sparing'. In Wallonia, some regions allow more extensive (beef) production. <p>There were no clear questions about what interviewees think might be an opportunity for advancing agroecology transition, so we don't have answers on that.</p>
Cyprus	<p>In general, it is considered that there are limited resources and policy support for advancing agroecology-based practices in Cyprus. The main barriers are structural and institutional and lack of communication and promotion of agroecology as a concept in the current agriculture systems. There are opportunities for fostering a transition towards agroecology in Cyprus because they are located in one of the hotter and driest climates in the EU. Therefore, Cyprus can be promoted as an open laboratory for assessing and developing more sustainable agricultural practices and climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies in the agriculture sector.</p>
Czech Rep.	<p>Note: Most respondents focused on the barriers, instead of the opportunities. Society fails to recognise that agroecology transition could answer many of the concerns they have already identified. Among the greatest barriers of advancing agroecology is the low level of understanding the complexity of agroecology and what the process of transition towards agroecology would entail. This is due to the lack of information available to all stakeholder groups. Societal demands are limited to the farming practices already addressed by the organic farming movement. Another significant barrier to the agroecology transition is the political culture, where intensive farming corporations have established significant influence on policy making and created an unwelcoming environment for initiatives that would put more pressure on farmers to comply with further sustainability requirements. Agroecology research does not receive enough support. The indicators and the requirements for deliverables used in conventional agricultural research cannot do justice</p>

	<p>to the complexity of the field of agroecology. Addressing this could be an opportunity. The lack of social capital that characterises the post-socialist countries, hence the unwillingness to cooperate, is a critical issue that prevents bottom-up strategic planning agroecology transition would require. Demonstration farms could become influential venues where the cooperation among farmers and other stakeholders could be coordinated, knowledge transfer should be encouraged, adaptation of foreign practices should be assisted and adjusted to the local circumstances. Unfortunately, the market structure does not seem to be ready to go beyond using CSR as a promotion technique. There is a lack of true dedication to support the creation of value chains that would acknowledge and promote certain social aspects of agroecology. Their actions are limited compared to the actual influence they could have.</p>
Denmark	<p>The main agricultural cropping systems in Denmark are linked with intensive livestock production (fodder crops, mostly cereals for pigs and maize for cattle) and there are limited incentives for diversifying land use. Where grasslands are relevant crops, they dominate to an extent that does not allow for them to benefit in a more diverse crop rotation. The market for other crops is small and especially for labour intensive production – except rapeseed, potatoes and a few vegetables. It was stated that it is important to focus on the development of new value chains for alternative crop and plant-based foods, incentives towards growing crops with longer growing season and mixed crops (needs industry engagement to ensure a market) as well as for using ICT and automation (precision farming) for reducing input. One interviewee said that “there is much that can be done, and we’ve just started. Biggest barrier is knowledge, how it can be done practically. And how we can explain it to the whole supply chain”. There are furthermore some challenges of Denmark being within international markets and we need to be rethinking traditional ways of selling products. Export is important to DK.</p>
Estonia	<p>There are not so many opportunities perceived as supportive for a transition towards agroecology-based practices and research infrastructures. However, the current European policies are generally agreed to sufficiently foster an agroecology transition. The current national policies are seen as slightly less fostering for an agroecology transition. The national contact points in Estonia agree to some extent that a transition towards agroecology-based practices is seen as a societal concern in Estonia. There is some disagreement on whether the current organisation of the food market supports agroecological initiatives. There are also opposing opinions on whether resource allocation is sufficient to support agroecology transition and on whether advisory systems are sufficiently fostering agroecology transition. However, there is agreement that the underlying values of the current agriculture and food production system do not sufficiently foster an agroecology transition.</p> <p>The most important barriers for an agroecology transition in Estonia are the general lack of awareness as well as insufficient understanding about the impact of agroecology. Also, the education on all levels is seen as a barrier. Moreover, the farming advisory system is very limited and not working towards agroecology. Also, the habits, especially the farmers’</p>

	<p>habits, are seen as a barrier since farmers are usually working on their farm as they are used to do it. However, some NCP do not perceive them as barriers, since only political decisions matter. Political decisions can lead the path towards agroecology by certain programmes.</p> <p>The well-being of the population is most important. An agroecology transition can only work if the population can afford agroecologically-produced products. However, If the general fertilisers and plant protection measures are getting more expensive, farmers need to find new solutions. Strong advisory services could help to lead the path towards an agroecology transition.</p>
Finland	<p>In Finland, neither the national policies, nor the European policies are seen as sufficiently fostering for an agroecology transition. Also resource allocation is not seen as sufficient to support agroecology transition. A transition towards agroecology is not seen as a societal concern in Finland. And the current organisations of food markets are not considered as supportive of the agroecological initiatives. The underlying values of the current agriculture and food production system are not seen to sufficiently foster an agroecology transition. Only the advisory systems are considered to foster agroecology transition to some extent.</p> <p>The overall structure of the food system is seen as the most important barrier for an agroecology transition in Finland. But also a lack of system understanding, a lack of communication and lack of cooperation were named as important barriers and additionally, that the subsidies system is based on hectares.</p> <p>The food culture in Finland should be given more value, especially regarding local food. There is not so much local diversity in foods in this country. Moreover, there is not so much discussion about local foods. Also, social aspects of agroecology in this country are not so much discussed yet. There should be an increase in information about which foods are there in this country and what can be improved in their production. Also, income opportunities for farmers need to be considered. Finland works as a part of the European food systems for ex. In dairy, for the high milk yield per cow, farmers rely on feed import. Thus, a redesign of the food system in Europe is demanded to be compatible with agroecology.</p>
France	<p>Long-term plans for action and practices need to be implemented while regulations need to be able to foresee difficulties to prevent falling into bottle-necks when the time of a project or the time of decision making politicians is due. Unfortunately, these long-term perspectives are often missing in France, but also within the EU. Resource allocation is for most of the interviewees not or only to a small regarded as sufficiently fostered, better for research than for the demonstration (e.g. through LLs) to support farmers. The advisory systems are efficiently working from the ministry perspective, but not from the research one. However, they claim that once there are sufficient innovative ideas for practices, it might be fast and relatively easy to convince the farmers of an agroecological approach. However, there are still plenty of other barriers to overcome. First, there are technical barriers, as not every crop can be planted everywhere and hence the technology has to be adapted, which can be complicated. Further, the government must be willing to think long-term</p>

	<p>and show real interest towards agroecology. The European Green Deal has to be implemented consequently in France and it has to be ensured that it will not be used for green-washing. Finally, developing new values different from the ones of the last 50 years might be difficult. The production should not only focus on quantity, but also on quality and make sure the impacts on the environment stay small. Furthermore, the dying generation of farmers and the lack of rural development must be stopped. Being a farmer must be more attractive again, especially to the younger generation which is growing up with the awareness of agroecology and its benefits.</p>
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key barriers of transitions to agroecology relate to knowledge exchange and education. Interviewees highlighted the need to improve the coverage of agroecology and related sustainability themes in the curricula of vocational schools but also more generally in education at all life stages (also to address identified differences in the understanding of the importance of a transition between different generations). This needs to be accompanied by awareness-raising programmes. Increased institutional support for training of advisors and farmers and strengthening multi-stakeholder networks could help addressing key barriers in relation to education, knowledge transfer. • Further opportunities for advancing an agroecology transition within the country were seen in strengthening producer-consumer linkages, e.g. building on the experience of food policy councils and through producer-consumer associations. • Opportunities were also identified in the research sector. It was noted that the current career reward system in research does not promote transdisciplinary research. Stronger acknowledgement of transdisciplinary research on agroecology was suggested. In addition, a shift in paradigm in research funding would enable funding of long term research on systemic changes and improvements of a transition to agroecology. Policy instruments play an important role in the promotion of transitions to agroecology by supporting good practices and regulating or banning bad practices.
Hungary	<p>Note: The respondents at this part of the interviewing process preferred to highlight those obstacles that need to be addressed before one could start focusing on the advance of the agroecology transition.</p> <p>The agrarian policies and the dynamics supported by the available subsidies are not supportive of such a transition. Policy makers seem to be “interested in keeping the status quo”. There are no substantive policy tools to actively support the transition. The agroecological policies are mainly market oriented and fail to call for the internalisation of the externalities of intensive agriculture. This keeps up their competitive advantage of being able to produce cheaply. Internalisation might level the playing field for those willing to implement agroecological measures and in order to have a lower impact on the environment. There is also a lack of dedication to assist farmers who apply to calls for the implementation of certain alternative agroecological practices. The farmers should ideally get sufficient information during the application process, and be offered technical assistance when they reach the point</p>

	<p>where they can implement these practices.</p> <p>Farmers also prioritise their short-term economic interest in their decision making. Due to their low level of understanding of agroecology, and their lack of insight into how the implementation of certain agroecological practices could benefit them, they stay away from these alternatives. Improving their awareness and engaging them through living labs or on-farm networks could change this dynamic. Even though the role of supportive policies is crucial for agroecology transition, farmers will not get on board unless they are convinced that these policies serve their interests.</p>
Iceland	<p>The advisor mostly disagreed that there are sufficient opportunities for advancing agroecology-based practices in Iceland. The main reason is the lack of knowledge about agroecology at all levels. Filling this knowledge gap is seen as a challenge, as there are no grassroots organisations that can support the integration and sharing of knowledge. The researcher had a different opinion and agreed that enough resources are allocated to support the agroecology transition. This suggests that knowledge that is relevant for the agroecology transition may be generated within research infrastructures, but different stakeholders are too disconnected to fully benefit from it. Overall, climate is a great obstacle to the implementation of some practices in Iceland, as it is not favourable to agricultural production and limits what can be done.</p>
Ireland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In general, it is considered that there are current national and European policies that can help to foster agroecology transition. However, there are not sufficient resources allocated or advisory systems sufficiently adapted to help this transition. • Barriers: Structural and institutional barriers. The perceptions and understanding of agroecology for mainstream stakeholders. Lack of understanding of the concept and considerable overlap between different concepts e.g., regenerative agriculture, organics, sustainable agriculture and agroecology. Environment legislation and policy seen as restrictions and constraining food production. Need to get to point where the environment and good ecological condition and functioning ecosystems are seen as the foundation of and integral to food production system. • Opportunities: Conceptually there should be consideration of a farm as a system and how all elements can be considered to reduce emissions, increase biodiversity, soil health, support farm incomes.
Latvia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities for advancing an agroecology transition within the country were seen in strengthening producer-consumer linkages, e.g. through producer-consumer associations and local and direct marketing. Potential was seen here in particular around the three main cities. • Interviewees highlighted the importance of learning about good practices from other countries showcasing how barriers and challenges of transitions towards agroecology have been overcome. This could include farm visits and integrated study tours of farmers, advisors, researchers and other stakeholders (the success of such study tours in the past was emphasised), e.g. as part of activities and funded within a European network, and also through activities on social media (e.g. including videos on youtube). Particular importance was emphasised on providing insights

	<p>on how agroecological farming can be profitable. Low profitability compared to more intensive conventional farming was highlighted as one of the key barriers of transition. Increased funding and institutional support for training of advisors and farmers and strengthening multi-stakeholder networks could help addressing key barriers in relation to education, knowledge transfer.</p>
Lithuania	<p>Increased funding and institutional support for training of advisors and farmers and strengthening multi-stakeholder networks could help addressing knowledge and competencies-related barriers. Agri-environment payments can favour the adoption and maintenance of agroecological practices, if adequately tailored to specific farming systems and adequately remunerating ecosystem services provided by farmers. Overall, interviewees indicated scope for better integration of agricultural and environmental policies to foster transition to agroecology (e.g. joint monitoring programmes). Increased involvement of Lithuanian researchers in European research projects can improve funding opportunities for setting up and running living labs on agroecology.</p>
Norway	<p>In Norway, there is some disagreement on whether the national policies, and the European policies sufficiently foster agroecology transition. The resource allocation, however, is generally not seen as sufficient to support agroecology transition in general. A transition towards agroecology is not seen as a societal concern in Norway. And the current organisation of food markets are not considered as supportive of the agroecological initiatives. The underlying values of the current agriculture and food production system are not seen to sufficiently foster an agroecology transition. Only the advisory systems are considered to foster agroecology transition to some extent. The most important barrier for an agroecology transition are incentives and perspectives, especially for the farmers. The competitive system for food is based on low prices and standard products in high volumes, which is not stimulating the transition towards agroecology. Moreover, the policy system seems to primarily stimulate industrial production. Only if farmers get a better livelihood by changing to agroecology, makes it probable that they change. Moreover, the perception of Norwegian food production is seen as clean and green. Thus, if everyone thinks that everything is fine as it is, no change will happen. Other barriers concern the lack of goals from the authorities and the food system which needs to be changed. Local distribution channels are an important stakeholder, that has not been considered yet. The value chain is not supporting agroecological principles. Alternative productions should be included as opportunities, such as organic farming, urban farming or direct sales from farmer to consumer. This would open up /break up the established industrial system. Additionally, there is a need for a different rhetoric. The term agroecology is not clear yet and it is not used. If the individual production methods are identified as agroecology-based, then it would be easier to discuss the opportunities for each individual method. Then the common vocabulary could also be used. Also, more (long-term) research is required to support and follow agroecological systems.</p>

Poland	Overall the interviewees struggled to identify opportunities. They stressed the need to address the disconnect between farming and research, the lack of national pro-agroecology policies, and the lack of demand for agroecological products.
Serbia	<p>The AE and valorisation of resources are the aims that everybody supports, while the financial backing remains the key driver and the mobilising factor in this process. In Serbia, AE debate was started through the organic production, which was recognised by the market.</p> <p>AE is based on organic production through its legislation and stipulated laws. For AE transition there is also a need to identify a period of up to five years where there could be a decrease in agricultural production (yields) due to transition to AE production practices, where the price of food can rise and where the agricultural system adjustments will be taking place, which is not an easy decision.</p> <p>There is a high motivation among farmers to learn and try new methods. There are also annual specialised courses (traditionally held each January at Zlatibor, Serbia) that provide consultations among agronomists and farmers. The seminars can attract up to 800 – 1000 participants.</p>
Slovakia	<p>Agroecology transition is at an early stage in Slovakia. Its main focus should be on increasing the general understanding of agroecology and providing tools and targeted support for those stakeholders who are willing to verify how agroecology could work for them. This requires building frameworks for cooperation between the research sector and the early bird stakeholders. Some policies with potential to indirectly support the inclusion of agroecological principles already present guidelines for that (e.g.: the National Strategy for the Protection of Biodiversity). Strategic planning should create space for new policies that would provide tools and sufficient support for the stakeholders willing to engage in agroecological practices.</p> <p>Lately there wasn't enough focus on the support of cooperation between research and production practices, which is recognised as the “big challenge” the ministries need to address. They expect that the AKIS database could also be used for this as a strategic tool, which provides an insight into the current research programmes, so they could be supported in a more efficient way to secure the implementation of their results.</p> <p>One of the most important barriers that agroecology transition faces in Slovakia is financial insufficiency due to the non-transparent approach to budget allocation that characterised the last few years. It is closely related to the farmers' poor motivation and their low trust. Also, there is no clear, long-term strategy developed by the government to mark a direction addressing the principles of agroecology in the Slovak agricultural sector. There is also a lack of understanding of agroecology even among the decision makers. Besides, there is too much focus on the economic efficiency of agriculture, and much less on the environmental and social aspects of it. Decisions are made out of fear of low production, aiming to secure all the available financial support. There should be more awareness-raising, so stakeholders could recognise the opportunities the implementation of agroecological practices hold for them. Further</p>

	<p>development of the organic farming sector could be a way to introduce more agroecological practices into the Slovak fields, through the over 1200 registered organic operations. There is also a range of agroecological practices that could be appealing to conventional farmers as well. These should be made more visible and attainable, by providing sufficient information about them - especially about their profitability. The bottleneck of agroecology transition in Slovakia consists of the lack of understanding of agroecology and the low social capital that characterises the region. Currently, at this initial stage, most measures focus on the promotion of production-oriented agroecological practices, and fail to address the range of available added values, the need to address issues relevant for the processing and market access. There is an absence of a functional advisory system. There should be calls suitable for supporting the cooperation between researchers, farmers and the administration, ideally in a quadruple helix with science, policy, industry and society working together.</p>
Switzerland	<p>Agroecology is powerful - in terms of the knowledge intensity, transdisciplinary, holistic approach, and scientific, traditional and local knowledge – there is so much potential in agroecology for society. He sees a great potential in getting young people involved in agriculture. If we live in agroecology we can get away from focusing on yields and shift towards sustainability. The complexity of agroecology and a holistic approach is where the power lies.</p> <p>The current survey does not account for mixed-crop livestock systems and leaves out core themes of agroecology.</p>
Turkey	<p>Studies on barriers for agroecology transition in the country are very limited. The importance of providing the farmers with necessary political will and financing opportunities to support transition is mentioned in national and international studies. Lack of knowledge about appropriate technologies and practices, land degradation and low youth participation in agriculture are some of these factors. The use of digitalisation potential in the agriculture sector is also important in order to increase agricultural production and productivity. Digital technologies, if adopted more broadly, can contribute to improve the sustainability of food systems. Technology transfer, farmer education and interdisciplinary approaches involving all actors (such as scientists, farmers, industry, governments) are required to increase the potential of the digital technologies.</p>
United Kingdom	<p>Advisory services are well developed, but are not oriented toward agroecology – but the strong extension service is an opportunity. There is a need to better understand the role of the private sector and the corporations, and their interest in maintaining the status quo. The dominance of supermarkets in the UK (97% of the market) is a big barrier. In this dominant market space, food produced agroecologically is seen as a sign of an alternative lifestyle approach, and relegated to Alternative Food Networks. For agroecology transition to work, good examples of how it can be profitable for growers and others in the supply chain are needed. Wales has a very strong community spirit and interest in its landscape, which could be leveraged, especially in collaboration with national parks. Fertiliser prices are going up, and this may force the industry's hand.</p> <p>AE4EU: Barriers: Financial barriers for farmers to shift to agroecology.</p>

	<p>Organic is a safer choice as it is linked with certification and a concrete market. There are strong vested interests in the agrochemical sector. There is a lack of knowledge around the transition. Opportunities: In Scotland there is a strong interest in and pride in food heritage and natural beauty which should be capitalised on. Overall in the UK there is a wave of interest in soil health and soil carbon which should be captured. There are also important local food-related initiatives, such as Sustainable Food Places, which should be linked with.</p>
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Pending online publication:

- *Funding Mechanisms for Agroecology Initiatives (D2.2),*
- *Overview of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures in Europe (D2.4),*
- *Agroecology open Innovation: Best cases across Europe (D2.5).*